

Study on the Population Growth of Different Earthworm Species (Annelida: Oligochaeta)

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Abstract

The study area was Vegetable and Fruit Research and Development Centre (VFRDC) at Hlegu. The study period was from June, 2013 to August, 2013. Three earthworm species, namely *Eudrilus eugeniae*, *Perionyn excavatus* and *Pheretima andamanensis* belonging to three genera and two families were selected for this study. Total population growth and morphological characters of these species, and chemical composition of vermicompost were examined.

Introduction

An earthworm is a tube-shaped, segmented animal commonly found living in soil that feeds on live and dead organic matter. From a total of around 6,000 species, only about 150 species are widely distributed around the world (Blakemore, 2012). The extensive earthworm fauna recorded a total of 170 earthworm species exist in Myanmar (Gates, 1972).

The main habitat of earthworm is in soil, the situation is more complicated than that. Earthworms are classified into three main ecophysiological categories: (1) leaf litter or compost-dwelling worm (epigeic) (2) topsoil-or subsoil dwelling worms (endogeics) and (3) anecic (meaning "reaching up") worms that construct permanent deep burrows through which they visit the surface to obtain plant material for food, such as leaves. Also two basic types of worms can be found those that feed on the surface and those that feed in the subsurface. The surface feeders eat plant residue, and are generally large worms and live in vertical burrows often over 1.83 m deep. Subsurface feeders are smaller than surface feeders (Bouche, 1977).

Earthworm populations depend on both physical and chemical properties of the soil, such as temperature, moisture, pH, salts, aeration, and texture, as well as available food and the ability of the species to reproduce and disperse. One of the most important environmental factors is pH, but earthworms vary in their preferences. The application of chemical fertilizers, sprays; and dusts are believed to have a disastrous effect on earthworm populations. The most reliable way to maintain or increase worm populations in the soil is to avoid the application of chemicals. The addition of organic matter, preferably as a surface mulch, on a regular basis will provide them with their food and nutrient requirements, and will create the optimum conditions of temperature and moisture that will stimulate their activity (Blakemore, 2012).

Various species of worms are used in vermiculture, the practice of feeding organic waste to earthworms to decompose food waste. The potential of earthworms is used in recycling of nutrients-waste management and development of vermicomposting systems at commercial scale. While the droppings, known as castings (vermicompost), help in enriching the soil, due to it being rich in phosphorous, magnesium, calcium, nitrogen and potassium as the important plant nutrients. Vermicompost also contains biological active substance such as plant growth regulators (Darwin, 1881).

Moreover, the worms themselves provide a protein source for animal feed. They have also been used for medicinal purposes ancient times in the treatment of illnesses such as bladder stones, jaundice, rheumatism, fever and impotency (Waldon, 1978). They are also high

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in Omega 3 essential oil which helps in lowering down the level of 'bad' cholesterol in the body (Singha, 2011).

Aim and Objectives

The present work aimed to assess the status of earthworms in the study area of Vegetable and Fruit Research and Development Centre (VFRDC) at Hlegu with the following objective.

- To assess the population growth of Earthworm species
- To investigate the fertility of vermicompost

Materials and Methods

Study Site and Study Period

Study site was Vegetable and Fruit Research and Development Centre (VFRDC) at Hlegu, Yangon Division. The study period was from June 2013 to August 2013 (Figure 1).

Specie of the Studied Earthworms

A total of three earthworm species (*Eudrilus eugeniae*, *Perionyx excavatus* and *Pheretima andamanensis*) under two families of Eudrilidae and Megascolecidae belonging to order Oligochaeta were selected (Table 1) and (Plate II). According to ecological category, they are epigeic species (Table 1).

Selection of Raw Materials and Earthworms

Raw materials for preparation of vermicompost were almond leaves, corn stalks and grasses. Farm yard manure (F.Y.M) was added to raw materials to enhance the formation of vermicompost. Three species were selected these experiments. Two species were introduced from India for the purpose of vermicompost production. One species is native to Myanmar (Plate I).

Preparation for Earthworm Production

Three Earthworm bins (height 1.2 meters, diameter 1.5 meters) cylindrical-shaped made of concrete were used. The first layer of dry leaves (grass and almond) with thickness of 4 inches was introduced into the bin. Second layer was 10 inches thick; it consisted of cow-dung and chopped corn stalks. Earthworms were then placed on the second layer. A total of 250 earthworm species for respective bins were added. The third layer was similar to second layer. Water was sprinkled on the bins to moisten the raw materials and to provide favourable conditions (temperature 25-30° C and moisture 40-45 %) for the earthworms. A wet gunny cloth was spread top of the bins. Composting materials were mixed manually from top to bottom twice a month. There were three bins used for each species in the present study (Plate I).

Data Collection

The numbers of earthworm were counted by hand sorting from the final product of vermicompost. It took 90 days to make vermicompost. Each sample of compost (250 g) was put into a labeled plastic bag and carried to the laboratory of Land-Used Department, Myanmar Agriculture Service to analyze the chemical contents (nitrogen, phosphorous, potassium, magnesium and calcium).

Identification

Identification of the selected earthworm species were made according to the method of Gates (1972).

Figure 1. Map of study area and study site at Hlegu.

Results

Morphometric Measurements and Morphological Characters of the Studied Earthworm Species

Morphometric measurements and morphological characters were presented in Tables 2 and 3, and Plate II.

Population Changes in the Three Different Species

A total of 250 individual earthworms were initially stocked in each bin. Bin A was used for *Eudrilus eugeniae* (African nightcrawler worm); Bin B was used for *Perionyx excavates* (Indian blue worm) and Bin C was for *Pheretima andamanensis* (local worm). After three months of composting, the total earthworm population in three bins were counted to be 917, 883 and 859, respectively (Figure 2). The earthworm population had increased by 667, 633 and 609 numbers. The population was 2.67, 2.53 and 2.44 times of initial number in the three bins respectively (Table 4, Figure 2).

Chemical Composition of Vermicompost by the Selected Earthworm Species

After three months of vermicomposting, sample of compost material from each bin was checked. Vermicompost from Bin A (*Eudrilus eugeniae*, African nightcrawler worm) had 1.25 percent of nitrogen, 0.99 percent of phosphorous, 0.90 percent of potassium, 1.27 percent of calcium and 1.29 percent of magnesium.

Bin B (*Perionyx excavatus*, Indian blue worm) had 2.45 percent of nitrogen, 1.03 percent of phosphorous, 1.11 percent of potassium, 1.70 percent of calcium and 1.29 percent of magnesium.

Bin C (*Pheretima andamanensis*, local worm) had 1.64 percent of nitrogen, 0.91 percent of phosphorous, 1.16 percent of potassium, 2.97 percent of calcium and 1.03 percent of magnesium (Table 5, Figure 3).

Compost in Bin B had highest nitrogen and phosphorous contents with potassium among the three bins.

Table 1. Selected Earthworm Species under Order Oligochaeta

No.	Family	Species name	Ecological category
1.	Eudrilidae	<i>Eudrilus eugeniae</i> (Kinberg, 1867) Africa nightcrawler worm	Epigeic
2.	Megascolecidae	<i>Perionyx excavatus</i> Perrier, 1872 Indian blue worm	Epigeic
3.	Megascolecidae	<i>Pheretima andamanensis</i> Michaelsen, 1907 Local worm	Epigeic

Table 2. Morphometric Measurements of the Studied Earthworm Species

No.	Species name	Length (mm)		Diameter (mm)		Segment no.	
		range	mean	range	mean	range	mean
1.	<i>Eudrilus eugeniae</i>	50-190	91	3-8	5	71-98	82.6
2.	<i>Preionyx excavatus</i>	60-120	94	3-5	4.1	47-87	61.6
3.	<i>Pheretima andamanensis</i>	100-160	125	4.5-6	5.2	61-96	74.5

Table 3. Morphological Characters of the Studied Earthworm Species

No.	Species name	Colour	Clitellum		Setae
			Location	Shape	
1.	<i>Eudrilus eugeniae</i>	Brown and red to violet	XIV-XVIII	Ventrally less developed	Lateral and ventral fused
2.	<i>Preionyx excavatus</i>	Dorsally, deep purple to reddish brown Ventrally, pale	XIII-XVII	Ring	Nil
3.	<i>Pheretima andamanensis</i>	Dorsally, dark brownish to violet grey	XIV-XVI	Ring	Slightly enlarged

Table 4. Population Growth of the Studied Earthworm Species after Three Months of Vermicomposting

No.	Species name	Common name	individuals			increment	
			initial	final	increased	times	%
1.	<i>Eudrilus eugeniae</i>	Africa night crawler worm	250	917	667	2.67	266.8
2.	<i>Preionyx excavatus</i>	Indian blue worm	250	883	633	2.53	253.2
3.	<i>Pheretima andamanensis</i>	Local worm	250	859	609	2.44	243.6

Table 5. Chemical composition of the vermicompost of each studied earthworm species

No.	Species name	Common name	N %	P %	K %	Ca %	Mg %
1.	<i>Eudrilus erageniae</i>	Africa night crawler worm	1.25	0.99	0.90	1.27	1.29
2.	<i>Preionyx excavatus</i>	Indian blue worm	2.45*	1.03*	1.11	1.70	1.29
3.	<i>Pheretima andamanensis</i>	Local worm	1.64	0.92	1.16*	2.97*	1.03

* shows the maximum value

Figure 2. Population changes (individual number) in vermicompost of studied earthworm species after three months

Figure 3. Comparison of chemical composition of vermicomposts of the three studied species

Discussion and Conclusion

A total of 250 individuals of each earthworm species were used in the present study. Two of three selected earthworm species, *Eudrilus eugeniae* and *Perionyx excavatus* were studied as an introduced species from India for the purpose of vermicompost production. A native earthworm, *Pheretima andamanensis* was studied together with them for comparison.

Viljoen and Reineck (1992) reported that in tropical and subtropical conditions the earthworm *Eudrilus eugeniae* appeared to be the best for vermicomposting. Anonymous (2009) informed that Indian blueworms, *Perionyx excavatus* were used in the tropics: they were introduced species in some area and adapted easily to living on food or plant waste in the confines of a bin. Suthar (2007) stated that *Eudrilus eugeniae* increased in total biomass much more rapidly than *Eisenia fetida*, a species which grows relatively well in most organic wastes.

In this study, the rate of population growth of *Eudrilus eugeniae* was greater than the other two tested species. *Eudrilus eugeniae* and *Perionyx excavatus*, both introduced species, were similar in their population growth. A local species, *Pheretima andamanensis* had slightly slower than the other two population growth. The analysis of chemical compositions of their vermicompost showed that the Indian blueworm seemed to generate more nitrogen and phosphorous than the other two species in vermicompost. But initial chemical composition of the vermicompost were not tested.

The study period of the work was during the wet season from June, 2013 to August, 2013. Three earthworm species, three genera belonging to two families under order Oligochaeta were studied for three months. The population growth was best in *E. eugeniae* among the three earthworm species within the three months. However, the Indian blue worm also had growth similar to *E. eugeniae*. The local worm had slower growth. The chemical compositions analysis of their vermicomposts revealed that they all generate nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium. Hence they would be useful to produce vermicompost for agriculture.

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A. Utilized raw materials

B. Selected earthworms

C. Earthworms' bin

Plate I. Raw materials, earthworm species and concrete bins utilized for vermicomposting.

A. *Eudrilus eugeniae*

B. Vermicompost of *E. eugeniae*

C. *Perionyx excavatus*

D. Vermicompost of *Pe. excavates*

E. *Pheretima andamanensis*

F. Vermicompost of *Ph. andamanensis*

Plate II. Studied earthworm species and their respective vermicomposts.